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EFFECTIVENESS OF REHABILITATION WITH THE PARTICIPATION OF MOTHERS IN PATIENTS WITH CEREBRAL PALSY

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ABSTRACT

Target. To study the role of physical culture in children's cerebral palsy. We examined 62 sick children with cerebral palsy. All the sick children were divided into two groups: basic and control. In addition to standard therapy, the children of the main group were also added therapeutic physical skills at home. The children of the main group became healthier, moral values were formed, and skills of independent activity were formed. Since cerebral palsy in children requires comprehensive rehabilitation, all forms of rehabilitation were comprehensively carried out in this study. It requires the participation of mothers, the effective participation of neurologists, rehabilitologists, massage therapists, speech therapists, kinesiologists, audiologists, and many other specialists. Only the joint participation of all specialists will ensure the great effect of rehabilitation. In this case, it is necessary to pay attention to the child's mentality, age, general condition, family conditions, and level of illness. When all the requirements are met, it can be observed that the effect will be higher

Keywords. Therapeutic gymnastics, cerebral palsy. practical help, effectiveness, treatment methods.

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ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ РЕАБИЛИТАЦИИ С УЧАСТИЕМ МАТЕРЕЙ БОЛЬНЫХ ДЦП**АННОТАЦИЯ**

Целью исследования является изучение роли и влияния лечебной физической культуры больным с детским церебральным параличом в домашних условиях. Исследовано нами 62 больные дети с церебральным параличом. Все больные дети были разделены на две группы- основную и контрольную. Детям основной группы, помимо стандартной терапии, добавили лечебную физическую культуру в домашних условиях вместе с матерей. У детей основной группы укрепилось здоровье, сформировались нравственные ценности, сформировались навыки самостоятельной деятельности. Поскольку ДЦП у детей требует комплексной реабилитации, в данном исследовании комплексно проводились все виды реабилитации. Оно требует участия матери, эффективного участия неврологов, реабилитологов, массажистов, логопедов, кинезитерапевтов, аудиологов и многих других специалистов. Только совместное участие всех специалистов обеспечит отличный эффект реабилитации. В этом случае необходимо обратить внимание на психику ребенка, возраст, общее состояние, семейные условия и уровень заболеваемости. При соблюдении всех требований можно заметить, что эффект будет выше. Лечебная физкультура должен быть необходимой составной частью лечения в домашних условиях вместе с матерей при ДЦП

Ключевые слова: лечебная гимнастика, церебральный паралич, дети, игровая форма, стандартное лечение, практическая помощь, эффективность, методы лечения.

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**BOLALAR BOSH MIYA FALAJI BOR BEMORLARDA ONALAR ISHTIROKIDAGI
REABILITASIYA SAMARADOROIGI****ANNOTATSIYA**

Bolalar bosh miya falajida davolovchi jismoniy tarbiyaning roli. Biz 62 ta bolalar bosh miyasi falaji bulgan bolalarni tekshirdik. Barcha bemor bolalar ikki guruxga bulindi. Asosiy guruxga standart terapiya bilan birga uy sharoitida onasi erdamida davolovchi jismoniy tarbiya kulladik. Bolalardagi miya yarim palsi murakkab reabilitatsiyani talab qilganligi sababli, ushbu tadqiqotda reabilitatsiyaning barcha turlari kompleks ravishda amalga oshirildi. Bunda onaning ishtiroki, nevropatologlar, reabilitatsiya bo'yicha mutaxassislar, massaj terapevtlari, nutq terapevtlari, kinezioterapevtlar, audiologlar va boshqa ko'plab mutaxassislarning samarali ishtiroki talab etiladi. Faqat barcha mutaxassislarning birgalikdagi ishtiroki mukammal reabilitatsiya effektini ta'minlaydi. Bunday holda, bolaning ruhiyati, yoshi, umumiy ahvoli, oilaviy sharoiti va kasallanish darajasiga e'tibor berish kerak. Agar barcha talablar bajarilsa, ta'sir yanada yuqori bo'lishini sezasis.

Uy sharoitida ona bilan birgalikda davolovchi jismoniy tarbiya bolalar bosh miya falajligida asosiy urin egallaydi.

Kalit so'zlar. Davolovchi jismoniy tarbiya, bosh miya falaji, bolalar, uyin usuli, standart davo. amaliy yordam, samaradorlik, davolash usullari.

Kirish: Miya falaji bachadonda, tug'ruq paytida, shuningdek, miyaning asosiy tuzilmalari hali etuk bo'lmagan yangi tug'ilgan davrda miyaning shikastlanishi natijasida rivojlanadi. Reabilitatsiyaning maqsadi - bemorning jismoniy va ijtimoiy moslashuvi va uning individual imkoniyatlarini kengaytirish. Yiliga bir yoki ikki marta klinik sharoitda reabilitatsiya ko'rinadigan natijalarni keltirmaydi. Shuning uchun biz onalar bilan birgalikda uyda jismoniy mashqlar qilishga

qaror qildik. Ota-onalar farzandini davolay oladi, boshqa shifokor emas. Ota-onalar butun kunini miya yarim palsi bilan kasallangan bolaga g'amxo'rlik qilishlari kerak. Jismoniy mashqlar bilan biz ishlashni tiklash uchun tanaga shifobaxsh va tiklovchi ta'sir ko'rsatishni xohlaymiz; neyrovaskulyar va metabolik kasalliklarni bartaraf etish yoki kamaytirish uchun ta'sirlangan hududda qon aylanishini va metabolik jarayonlarni yaxshilash, asab qobig'i va atrofdagi to'qimalar o'rtasida yopishqoqlik paydo bo'lishining oldini olish va agar bu yopishishlar mavjud bo'lsa, sog'lom to'qimalarning yopishqoq shakllanishlarga moslashish qobiliyatini rivojlantirish. ; zaiflashgan mushaklarni kuchaytirish, harakatlarni muvofiqlashtirishni tiklash, bog'liq kasalliklarga qarshi kurashish: vertebra egriligi va cheklangan harakatchanligi.[2]

Tadqiqot usullari: Ushbu ish miya yarim falajining turli shakllari bilan og'rigan 84 nafar bemorni o'rganish natijalariga asoslangan. Bolalarning yoshi 1 yoshdan 4 yoshgacha. Biz ularni ikki guruhga ajratdik. Birinchi 32 bola - 50%; ikkinchi 32 bola - 50%. Ikkala guruh ham standart davolash, massaj, jismoniy davolash oldi. Ushbu muolajalarga qo'shimcha ravishda biz nazorat guruhiga uyda fizika terapiyasini buyurdik. Biz ota-onalarga ushbu mashqlarni uyda davom ettirishni o'rgatganmiz. Har bir bola uchun alohida individual mashqlar berildi. Biz har bir bola muntazam ravishda bajarishi kerak bo'lgan oddiy, samarali usullarni belgilab berdik. Jismoniy protseduralar issiq o'ramlardan, kerosinli ilovalardan iborat bo'lib, ular qo'shma qattiqlikni oldini olish uchun amalga oshiriladi. Miya falajida ishlatiladigan dorilar qon aylanishini yaxshilaydi va shu bilan mushak va asab to'qimalarining ovqatlanishini yaxshilaydi. Bir tomondan, shikastlangan miyani qayta tiklashga imkon beradigan hech qanday davolash yo'q.[3] Biroq, agar siz ilmiy asoslangan dastur bo'yicha ishlasangiz, u holda buzilmagan holatda bo'lgan asab tizimi barcha funktsiyalarini bajarishi mumkin. Jismoniy mashqlar terapiyasi mashg'ulotlari bola tug'ilgandan so'ng, asta-sekin asoratlar bilan boshlanishi juda muhimdir. Bundan tashqari, agar bolada miya yarim palsi belgilari bo'lmasa ham, uning rivojlanishiga moyil bo'lsa ham, darslarni boshlash kerak. Jismoniy tarbiya dasturlari miya yarim palsi bilan kasallangan bolalarni har tomonlama rehabilitatsiya qilishda etakchi o'rin tutadi. Biz miya yarim palsi bilan og'rigan har bir bemorning motor muhitining xususiyatlarini diqqat bilan tahlil qildik va vosita funktsiyasini rag'batlantirishga imkon beradigan dastur yaratdik. [1] Mashqlar to'plamini tuzishda miya yarim palsi bilan og'rigan bemorlarga, mushaklarning harakatlariga e'tibor berish kerak. Miya falaji bilan og'rigan bemorlarda sezgi kuchi etishmaydi va bu jismoniy mashqlar dasturi orqali ma'lum darajada tuzatilishi mumkin. Biz quyidagi mashqlar bilan ishladik:

-Mushaklarni cho'zish mashqlari: mushaklarning kuchlanishini engillashtiradi, teratogenezni oldini oladi, harakat oralig'ini oshiradi

.-Mushaklarning sezgirligini rivojlantirish, mushaklarning ma'lum bir sohasini tartibga solish imkonini beradigan kuch hosil qilish uchun mashqlar

.-Nerv sezgirligini o'rgatish orqali nerv to'qimalarining funksional holatini yaxshilash mashqlari

.- Organlar faoliyatining samaradorligini saqlab qolish uchun chidamlilik mashqlari.

- Spazmlar, kuchlanish va kramplarni bartaraf etish uchun bo'shashish mashg'ulotlari.

-Yurish mashqlari (normal yurishni o'rganish uchun).[2]

-Muvozanat va vosita kuchini yaxshilash uchun toqqa chiqish mashqlari

.-Qarshilik mashqlari: Mushaklar kuchini rivojlantirish uchun qarshilik mashqlarini asta-sekin oshiring.

Darslarning davomiyligi - yosh bolalar uchun - kuniga 2-3 marta 15 daqiqadan ko'p bo'lmagan; o'rta va katta yoshdagi bolalar uchun kuniga 3-4 marta 20-30 daqiqa.

Miya falaji bilan og'rigan odamlar asta-sekin intensivlikdagi mashqlarni bajarish orqali mushaklar kuchini rivojlantirishlari mumkin.[5] Og'irlik markazi tananing har ikki tomonida bir tekis taqsimlanishini ta'minlash uchun mashqlar birinchi navbatda bir oyoq va qo'l bilan, keyin ikkinchisi bilan bajarildi. Zaiflashgan qismga ko'proq yuk qo'yildi va shuning uchun harakat yaxshilandi. Biz miya yarim palsi uchun mashqlar terapiyasi mashqlarini maxsus ishlab chiqdik, bu bizga bemorning motor qobiliyatini rivojlantirish va mustahkamlash imkonini berdi. Qorin bo'shlig'i mushaklarini rivojlantirish va mustahkamlash uchun zarur bo'lgan bir qator mashqlarni bajardik.

Biz barcha harakatlar to'g'ri bajarilishiga ishonch hosil qildik, chunki ular eslab qolinadi, odat bo'lib qoladi va o'zini o'zi ta'minlash shartiga aylanadi. Muvaffaqiyat deyarli butunlay ota-onalarga bog'liq, chunki shifokor, fizioterapiya mutaxassisi yoki massaj terapevti protseduralarni to'g'ri bajarishi mumkin, ammo ular juda oz vaqt talab qilishi mumkin. Ota-onalar uyda maxsus usullardan foydalangan holda, imkon qadar bolani mustaqil hayotga tayyorlashlari kerak.[6] Miya falajini tashxislash, klinik ko'rinishga asoslanib, kasallikning turini, bemorning yoshini va ahvolining og'irligini hisobga olgan holda, biz massaj, fizioterapiya va dori-darmonlarni davolashni buyurdik. Jismoniy mashqlar bilan bir qatorda, turmush tarzi rejimi qo'shildi, unda ortopedik yordamlar qo'llaniladi, nutq terapevti bilan bosqichma-bosqich mashg'ulotlar.

Tadqiqot natijalari: Chunki miya yarim palsi bilan mushak tonusi buziladi, bu esa keyinchalik patologik vosita reaksiyalarining shakllanishiga, muvozanatni saqlash va tortishish kuchiga qarshi turishda qiyinchiliklarga olib keladi. Kelajakda bu ham oyoq-qo'llarning kontrakturasi va deformatsiyasining shakllanishiga olib keladi. Reabilitatsiyaning eng samarali va samarali vositalaridan biri bu miya falajli bolalar uchun uy sharoitida mashqlar bilan davolashdir.[7] Uyda fizika terapiyasini davom ettirgan guruhlar bolaning harakatlarini inhibe qilish va ularni boshqarish qobiliyatini rivojlantirishga yordam berdi. Mashqlar muvofiqlashtirishni yaxshiladi va harakat doirasini oshirdi. Uzoq muddatli jismoniy terapiya orqali biz bolaga uy-ro'zg'or ko'nikmalarini, asosiy mehnat faoliyati haqida bilimlarni, ota-ona yordamisiz o'z-o'zini parvarish qilishni, yangi ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishni, shuningdek, to'g'ri harakatlarni o'rgatdi.[5] Biz mashqlar terapiyasini bir qator printsiplarga asosladi: - muntazam va tizimli mashqlar; - uzoq tanaffuslar yo'qligi; - jismoniy faollikni bosqichma-bosqich oshirish; - boshqa bemorlarga yo'naltirilmaslik - faqat individual usullar; - rivojlanish bosqichini hisobga olgan holda kasallik, bolaning yoshi, uning psixologik holati.

Ota-ona bilan birgalikda tuzatuvchi-yallig'lanish ishlarini olib bordik va bu bizga buzilgan funktsiyalarni qoplashga imkon berdi. Mashg'ulotlarni erta yoshdan boshlab o'tkazish tavsiya etilgan. Bola uchun qanchalik tezroq bo'lsa, shuncha yaxshi bo'ladi. Qo'llarning nozik motorli ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish kerak. Materiallar bo'lishi mumkin: konuslar, novdalar, toshlar, barglar, mevalar va sabzavotlar.

Jismoniy mashqlar bilan davolash tananing umumiy holatiga shifobaxsh ta'sir ko'rsatdi. Bolaning tanasida to'qimalar va organlarni mustahkamlashga yordam berdi. U zaiflashgan mushaklarni faollashtirdi, orqa miya egriligini tuzatdi, metabolizmni va boshqa metabolik jarayonlarni yaxshiladi, miya faoliyatini faollashtirdi va qon aylanishini tezlashtirdi. Agar bola o'z-o'zidan yurishda qiyinchilik tug'dirsa yoki o'z-o'zidan yurmasa, mashg'ulotlar panjaralar yoki qattiq tayanchlar yonida boshlandi, so'ngra qattiq arqondan zaiflashganga o'tadi. Biz individual reabilitatsiya davolash dasturini tuzdik. U innovatsion texnik vositalar - simulyatorlar, qurilmalar va apparat-dasturiy ta'minot tizimlaridan foydalangan holda, vosita mahoratini rivojlantirishning zamonaviy texnologiyalariga asoslangan.[5] Biz miya yarim palsi uchun reabilitatsiya dasturini alohida tanladik, ammo har bir kompleksda fizika terapiyasi majburiy edi. Jismoniy terapiya bilan biz tabiiy vosita funktsiyalarini va bolaning asosiy harakatlarni o'zlashtirishini tiklashga harakat qildik. Boshqa usullar bilan birgalikda jismoniy tarbiya asosiy maqsadga erishishga yordam berdi - bolani to'liq hayot bilan ta'minlash.[6]

Klinik va uy sharoitida miya falajiga qarshi mashqlar terapiyasi quyidagi natijalarga erishishga imkon berdi:

- chaqaloqning asosiy ko'nikmalari va qobiliyatlari rivojlangan;
- mushaklar kuchlanishining pasayishi;
- bo'g'imlarning egiluvchanligi va harakat doirasi oshishi;
- takomillashtirilgan muvozanat va muvofiqlashtirish
- yurak-qon tomir tizimini mustahkamlash;
- spazmlar va konvulsiyalarning chastotasini kamaytirish va to'liq bartaraf etish;
- asab tizimining sezuvchanligi oshishi;

Bolalar uchun to'g'ri ovqatlanishga alohida e'tibor berildi. Asos sifatida, bunday tashxis qo'yilgan bolalarga hamma narsa berilishi mumkin: meva, sabzavot, go'sht, baliq. Bunday bolalarni sut bilan ta'minlash ayniqsa muhimdir. Bu bolalar ayniqsa mehr va e'tiborga muhtoj. Faqat bu ularni davolay oladi. Onalar toza havoda ko'proq yurishlari kerak. Kasallik qanday qilib magistralga ko'tarilib, o'tib ketishini aqlan tasavvur qilishingiz kerak. Ular onalarni bolalarini iloji boricha tez-tez tabiat bilan aloqada qoldirishga majbur qilishdi.

Jismoniy faollik tanaga maxsus ogohlantiruvchi ta'sir ko'rsatdi, bu uning to'liq ishlashini ta'minlashi mumkin edi. Jismoniy mashqlar paytida markaziy asab tizimining harakat sohasining qo'zg'alish darajasi sezilarli darajada oshdi.[2] Ularda qo'zg'alish o'choqlari paydo bo'lib, patologik jarayonning sababi bo'lgan mexanizmlarning yo'q bo'lib ketishiga yordam berdi. Boshqacha qilib aytadigan bo'lsak, og'riqli fokus, xuddi bloklangan va buning natijasida buzilgan funktsiyalar asta-sekin normal holatga qaytadi. Muntazam jismoniy mashqlar standart davolash usullari bilan birgalikda nafaqat og'riqdan xalos bo'lishga yordam berdi, balki qaytarib bo'lmaydigan ko'rinadigan patologik jarayonlarni normallashtirishga yordam berdi. Terapevtik gimnastika bir vaqtning o'zida mushaklarni mashq qilish bilan umurtqa pog'onasining tabiiy yengilligini ta'minladi va butun terapevtik kompleksning bir qismidir. Mashqlar psixoterapevtik ta'sir ko'rsatdi.

Yengil va og'riqsiz harakatlar farovonlikni yaxshiladi va qattiqlashtiruvchi ta'sir ko'rsatdi.[5]

Xulosa. Kutilayotgan yakuniy natijalar: Jismoniy mashqlar, albatta, ona bilan uyda amalga oshirilishi kerak. Bu mashqlar bolalar salomatligini mustahkamlaydi, sog'lom turmush tarziga to'g'ri munosabatni shakllantiradi; axloqiy qadriyatlarni shakllantiradi: mehribonlik, rahm-shafqat, sezgirlik, do'stlik; bolalarning mustaqil faoliyat ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi.[7] Bizning biznesimizdagi asosiy narsa dangasa bo'lmaslik, balki maqsadimizga qat'iy intilishdir.

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